

ISic0036

I.Sicily inscription 0036

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. hic requiescit in pace Munatia Eul[alia]
2. religiosa femina quae vixit anno[s]
3. pl(us) m(inus) LXX deposita sub die pridie nona(s)
4. februaras Dydamio Sieidio vv(iris) cc(larissimis)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491826

EDR 137864

EDCS 22100030

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7329 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650794>)

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Diehl, Ernst Johann L. 1913. Lateinische altchristliche Inschriften, mit einem Anhang jüdischer Inschriften, ausgewählt und erklärt von E. Diehl. 2. Aufl. *Kleine Texte für Vorlesungen u Übungen*. Bonn. At no.99

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